

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 12

Acceptance of papers **December, 2025**

**Acceptance of
papers**

Published monthly

Topics

economics,
technology, social
sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Electronic publication, Issue 12. 531 pages.
Approved for publication on December, 2025.

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Professor, Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), (Malaysia)

Asongu Simplicie
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD), USA

Abdikarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Alimardonov Ilkhom Muzrabshokovich
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

CONTENTS

THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF APPLYING TAX INCENTIVES FOR INVESTMENTS DIRECTED TOWARD HUMAN CAPITAL	14
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF CASHLESS SETTLEMENTS AMONG ECONOMIC ENTITIES.....	21
Ruzimuradov Shukhrat Khusanovich	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM BRAND MARKETING IN MODERN CONDITIONS (UAE: DUBAI ON THE EXAMPLE OF A CITY).....	26
Ibodova Dilsora Ibodovna	
CREDIT DEFAULT SWAPS AS A WAY TO HEDGE AGAINST FORTHCOMING FUTURE UNCERTAINTIES IN THE DEBT MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN	31
Abduganiev Abdulaziz Alisher o'g'li	
SHOULD THE REGULATION OF THE E-COMMERCE MARKET IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN BE CARRIED OUT BY THE NATIONAL AGENCY FOR PERSPECTIVE PROJECTS OR THE CENTRAL BANK?	39
Sadikov Aziz Mirsharapovich	
MECHANISM FOR IMPLEMENTING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE OPERATIONS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	46
Bakhriddin Berdiyarov	
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES OF SMALL BUSINESSES IN THE INDUSTRY AND CONSTRUCTION SECTORS AND THEIR IMPACT ON EMPLOYMENT.....	53
Ergasheva Nigora Abdigapparovna	
AI-BASED NORMALIZATION METHODOLOGY FOR COLLECTING AND PROCESSING KPI INDICATORS.....	56
Shuhratov Mamurjon Shuhrat o'g'li	
REFORMS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PARTICIPATORY BUDGETING INITIATIVE IN UZBEKISTAN	63
Khamidov Khabibullo Hikmatulla ugli	
PROBLEMS OF THE INWARD PROCESSING CUSTOMS REGIME AND WAYS TO ELIMINATE THEM.....	70
Abdullaev Shakhzodbek	
FINANCIAL ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN CONSTRUCTION	74
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
MEASURES TO ENHANCE THE ROLE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF SMALL BUSINESS IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	80
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION.....	84
Alijonova Marjonabonu Jaxongir qizi	
INDIA'S EXPERIENCE IN ENHANCING PUBLIC WELFARE THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY	88
Aripov Oybek Abdullayevich	
GREEN STRUCTURAL TRANSFORMATION IN UZBEKISTAN: GREEN FINANCE AND ECO-INNOVATION FOR SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIAL AND AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT.....	93
Egamberdiev Khumoyun	
AGRICULTURAL MANAGEMENT BASED ON INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES AT THE INTERNATIONAL LEVEL: THE EXAMPLE OF UZBEKISTAN.....	101
Bustonov Komiljon Kumakovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE FINANCIAL CONDITION OF ENTERPRISES: ASSESSMENT OF EQUITY EFFICIENCY	110
Umurkul Shukhratovich Fayziev	

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	118
Mamadaliyev Akmaljon	
МЕТОДЫ И МЕХАНИЗМЫ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛЬСКОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ НА ТУРИСТСКОМ РЫНКЕ.....	124
Нурматова Ситора Шавкатовна	
ANALYSIS OF INNOVATION ACTIVITIES.....	133
Alieva Elnara Ametovna	
METHODS AND MECHANISMS FOR STUDYING CONSUMER BEHAVIOR IN THE TOURISM MARKET.....	139
Nurmatova Sitora Shavkatovna	
ALGORITHMS AND METHODS FOR CALCULATING THE AREA OF A GASTRIC ULCER DEFECT USING MODERN MATHEMATICAL TECHNIQUES.....	145
Yusupov Ibrohimbek XXX, Abdusamatova Munira Sultonbek qizi	
UTILIZATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN ENTERPRISE MARKETING ACTIVITIES.....	151
Sadikov Shohrux Shukhratovich	
ENSURING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS, GLOBAL TRENDS, AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS.....	156
Inomiddin Imomov	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY.....	161
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
IMPORTANT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF E-COMMERCE SERVICES.....	169
Jurakulov Shohruh Bahtiyorovich	
AGRICULTURE PROMOTION AND DEVELOPMENT IN MOUNTAIN AND MOUNTAIN REGIONS.....	173
Abdulxayeva Gulshan Maxmudovna	
IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES.....	178
Seytimbetov Kabul Serimbetovich	
INTEGRATION OF INTELLIGENT CONTROL IN DRYING SYSTEMS: PROCESS OPTIMIZATION THROUGH SENSORS, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, AND MODULAR DRYING.....	184
Yangiboyeva Raxbaroy Mashrabboy qizi	
THEORETICAL MODELS AND CONCEPTS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN THE ENERGY SECTOR.....	190
Nigmatullaeva Gulchekhra Nurullaevna	
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC POTENTIAL (A CASE STUDY OF NAMANGAN REGION).....	196
Tursinbayev Azizbek Nabijon o'g'li, Sirojiddinov Kamoliddin Ikromiddinovich	
DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING INVESTMENT AND EXPORT IN REMOTE SERVICE ENTERPRISES.....	203
Uzakov Ortik Shaymardanovich	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING THE INCOME OF THE POPULATION IN THE REGION.....	207
Kuldasheva Maftuna Musurmon kizi	
KEY FACTORS OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENT THROUGH SUBSIDIES AND INVESTMENTS TO INCREASE AGRICULTURAL CROP PRODUCTION IN UZBEKISTAN.....	211
Mamatkulova Nadira Makkamovna	
RAQAMLI MARKETING VA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA EKOTIZIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH USULLARI.....	216
Sobirov Azizbek Avazbekovich	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF FRUIT AND VEGETABLE PRODUCTION PROCESSES AND EXPORT POTENTIAL IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	223
Anorboeva Bakhtijamol Daniyar kizi	

THE IMPACT OF DEGRADATION ON THE OPERATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES UNDER SHARPLY CONTINENTAL CLIMATIC CONDITIONS	229
Qurbanov Yunus Murtaza o'g'li	
INTEGRATED NEW MEDIA OPERATION MODEL FOR INTELLIGENT TALENT ASSESSMENT PLATFORMS: THE PATH OF QR CODE ACTIVATION AND CONTENT-DRIVEN ENGAGEMENT.....	235
Wang Biao	
METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR SHAPING THE CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF YOUNGER PUPILS IN SOLVING MATHEMATICAL PROBLEMS	239
Dzhurakulova Adolat Khalmuratovna	
SOLIDWORKS-BASED MODELING OF AN AIR-BLOWING SYSTEM TO ENSURE HIGH-QUALITY FIBER REMOVAL FROM SAW TEETH	247
Mirzakarimov Mirsharoffiddin Mirzaabdurahimovich	
THEORETICAL STUDY OF TEMPERATURE AND THERMAL PHENOMENA IN MECHANICAL CUTTING OF WHITE CAST IRON.....	256
Allanazarov Akmal Abdulxaqovich	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY	262
Turdiyev Ulug'bek Qayumovich	
THE INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MIGRATION AND THE INDUSTRIAL ECONOMY	266
Khusanbek Begmatov	
THE IMPACT OF ESG PRINCIPLES ON THE HOTEL INDUSTRY	271
Khusenova Mekhrangiz	
CURRENT STATUS OF INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION AND SERVICES MARKET IN KASHKADARYA REGION.....	276
Norov Murodjon Makhmudovich	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASED CYBERSECURITY SYSTEM FOR THE AUTOMATIC DETECTION OF FAKE FINANCIAL RECEIPTS, PHISHING URLS, AND MALICIOUS APK FILES	284
Shermatov Axlidin Sharobiddin o'g'li	
WAYS TO INCREASE REVENUES IN COMMERCIAL BANK OPERATIONS	287
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
РОЛЬ СВОБОДНЫХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОН В РЕГИОНАЛЬНОМ РАЗВИТИИ И ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ	301
Файзиева Ширин Шодмоновна	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA IQTISODIY O'SISH OMILLARINING TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASI.....	307
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
FINTECH TRENDS: NEW TOOLS FOR ATTRACTING FINANCING IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	313
Madjitova Lolakhon Lazizovna	
CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF E-COMMERCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....	317
Toshpulatov Akhror Tukhtamurod ugli	
STRATEGIC DETERMINANTS OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	326
Rustamov Foziljon	
TYPES AND MEANS OF ADVERTISING IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM	335
Bahriyeva Zarina Nasimovna	
INTELLECTUALIZATION OF TECHNICAL MEANS FOR CONTROLLING TECHNOLOGICAL REFINING PROCESSES.....	340
Ruziyev Umidjon Abdimajitovich	
NECESSITY OF ENSURING AND INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF PLACEMENT MEANS	349
Sherkulov Dilshod Jurakulovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA MOLIYAVIY INKLYUZIYANING O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK NAZARIYALARI.....	354
Adashaliyev Baxtiyorjon Valisher o'g'li	

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE AUDIT OF LEASING OPERATIONS ON FARMS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	359
Tursunov Ulugbek Sativoldievich	
METHODOLOGY DEVELOPMENT RETAIL MARKETING AND TRADING SYSTEM.....	365
Makhmatkulov Golibjon Kholmuminovich	
NECESSITY OF ENSURING AND INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF PLACEMENT MEANS	369
Sherkulov Dilshod Jurakulovich	
ENVIRONMENTAL FISCAL POLICY AS A DRIVER OF GREEN GROWTH AND EMPLOYMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE	374
Rakhmatova Zilola Yurevna	
ON THE ISSUE OF CALCULATING THE POWER REQUIRED TO HEAT THE EDGES OF THE PIPE BILLET TO THE WELDING TEMPERATURE.....	379
Zairkulov Elyor Yoqubjon o'g'li	
STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF REGIONAL ELECTRICITY GENERATION VOLUMES.....	385
Doliev Shokhabbos Kulmurat ugli	
ANALYSIS OF ICT APPLICATION IN UZBEKISTAN'S TOURISM BASED ON EMPIRICAL RESEARCH.....	389
Nazarov Khusanbek Avazbek ogli	
METHODOLOGY FOR FORECASTING AND ANALYZING MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING INDICATORS AT AN ENTERPRISE.....	395
Minutdinova Liliya Tagirovna	
WELLNESS TOURISM AS AN ESSENTIAL COMPONENT OF HEALTH TOURISM.....	402
Tashtayeva Saida Kahharovna	
THE EXPERIENCE OF GERMANY IN DEVELOPING SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES.....	409
Annaklichev Saxi Saparmuxamedovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF THE INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ON AUDITING "ANALYTICAL PROCEDURES" IN NATIONAL AUDIT ACTIVITIES	416
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeyzinovich	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF GREEN ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT IN ENSURING REGIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY	421
Khamidillo Odilov	
A REALIST-POSITIVIST FRAMEWORK FOR ANALYSING MERGERS AND ACQUISITIONS UNDER ECONOMIC POLICY UNCERTAINTY	429
Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich	
DEVELOPING MATHEMATICAL MODELS TO SIMULATE THE DYNAMIC BEHAVIOR OF SEPARATION PROCESSES, CONSIDERING THE IMPACT OF EXTERNAL FACTORS	436
Abdulleva Kamola Rustamovna	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TRANSFORMATION OF BANKS.....	445
Umarova Malika Baxtiyarovna	
ON THE ISSUE OF RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT OF A SLAG-FORMING BASE FOR ELECTRODE COATINGS FOR WEAR-RESISTANT SURFACING.....	451
Sadikov Jaxongir Nasidjanovich	
MODELING OF HEAT FLOWS IN GAS-FIRED CHAMBER FURNACES.....	456
Rajabov Azamat Toirovich	
DEVELOPMENT OF A MIMO MODEL OF AZEOTROPIC DISTILLATION	462
Shamsutdinova Vineri Khafizovna	
THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INTERACTION OF A COTTON TUFT WITH A SCREW CONVEYOR AND A MESH SURFACE.....	468
Matyaqubova Jumagul Bakhtiyarovna	
FORECASTING LIQUIDITY AND SOLVENCY INDICATORS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE	473
Zaynutdinov Ismoil Samariddin o'g'li	
MODELS FOR PREDICTING THE MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES AND PRODUCTIONS	477
Gulyamov Shukhrat Mannapovich	

WAYS TO ADJUST LAND RESOURCE USE MECHANISMS FOR FARMERS BASED ON THE EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES.....	482
Akhmatov Abutolibkhon Ochilkhon oglu	
STATE SUPPORT MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MACHINE-BUILDING INDUSTRY	487
Xursandov Komiljon Makhmatkulovich	
EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF TOURISM FLOW FORECASTING IN CENTRAL ASIA BASED REGRESSION MODELS	491
Suratova Mokhirakhon Shavkat Kizi	
THE ROLE OF LOANS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGIONAL ECONOMY.....	498
Meylikov Fazliddin Abduhalim o'g'li, Valiev Oybek Shukhrat ugli	
PROPAGATION OF SMALL MOTIONS IN A TWO-LAYER DISPERSE MEDIA FLOW.....	503
D. S. Yakhshibaev	
FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE AUTOMATION SYSTEM OF ELECTRONIC SERVICES AND TOURIST PERMITS.....	511
Najmiddinov Sultan Nurali ugli	
THE NECESSITY OF DISCLOSING INFORMATION ON SELLING EXPENSES IN ACCOUNTING REPORTS OF PHARMACEUTICAL ENTERPRISES.....	516
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
INVESTMENT FINANCIAL MECHANISMS AND THEIR ROLE IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	521
Karjavova Khurshida Abdumalikovna	
WESTERN COUNTRIES' EXPERIENCES IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANKING ACTIVITIES.....	526
Alimjanova Dilrabo Sobirjanovna	

WESTERN COUNTRIES' EXPERIENCES IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF BANKING ACTIVITIES

Alimjanova Dilrabo Sobirjanovna

Independent Researcher,
Tashkent International University
Email: d.alimjanova@tmci.uz
ORCID: 0009-0007-3391-3526

Abstract: The article examines the formation of the financial performance of commercial banks and its theoretical foundations. Scientific conclusions and approaches of foreign and domestic scholars aimed at identifying the specific characteristics of the efficiency of banks' financial activities are systematized. In conducting the study, attention is focused on systematizing ideas proposed in international academic research and analyzing their impact on the formation of financial performance from the perspective of countries' experiences. Based on banks' financial indicators, scientific and practical approaches aimed at ensuring performance have been developed.

Key words: financial stability, profitability, asset quality, capital adequacy, cost-to-income ratio, interest and non-interest margin.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada tijorat banklari faoliyatining moliyaviy natijadorligining shakllanishi va uning nazariy asoslari tadqiq etilgan. Xorijiy va mahalliy olimlarning banklarning moliyaviy faoliyati samaradorligining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini aniqlashga qaratilgan ilmiy xulosa va yondashuvlar tizimlashtirilgan. Biz tadqiqotimizni amalga oshirishda xalqaro maydondagi ilmiy tadqiqotlarda ilgari surilayotgan g'oyalarni tizimlashtirish va ularning mamlakatlar tajribasi nuqtayi nazaridan moliyaviy natijadorlikni shakllantirishga ta'sirini tahlil qilishga e'tibor qaratilgan. Banklarning moliyaviy ko'rsatkichlari asosida natijadorlikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan ilmiy va amaliy yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: moliyaviy barqarorlik, rentabellik, aktivlar sifati, kapital yetarliligi, xarajatlarning daromadga nisbati, foizli va foizsiz marja.

Аннотация: В статье исследуются формирование финансовой результативности деятельности коммерческих банков и ее теоретические основы. Систематизированы научные выводы и подходы зарубежных и отечественных ученых, направленные на выявление специфических особенностей эффективности финансовой деятельности банков. В ходе исследования особое внимание уделено систематизации идей, выдвигаемых в международных научных исследованиях, а также анализу их влияния на формирование финансовой результативности с точки зрения опыта различных стран. На основе финансовых показателей банков разработаны научные и практические подходы, направленные на обеспечение результативности.

Ключевые слова: финансовая устойчивость, рентабельность, качество активов, достаточность капитала, соотношение расходов и доходов, процентная и непроцентная маржа.

INTRODUCTION

Assessing and evaluating the financial performance of banks requires an analysis of a number of foreign experiences. It should be noted that the financial performance of commercial banks is largely reflected in their level of profitability and the scale of return generation. At present, it is possible to observe the existence of various scientific approaches to determining banks' financial performance based on both financial and non-financial factors.

In classical theory, banks' financial performance is primarily explained through their ability to form margins, although this theoretical approach is currently undergoing transformation. In general, defining financial performance solely through profitability and return indicators represents a distinctive feature of classical views. This, in turn, reflects the close integration of banks' financial performance with the category of stability. From this perspective, many studies grounded in classical approaches also demonstrate that banks' financial performance is expressed through profitability and return indicators.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In our research, we initially focus on the U.S. banking system and the specific features of modern financial policy within it. In U.S. banks, financial performance is determined not only by lending activity but also by the priority role of non-interest income. Financial performance is strengthened through commission income, consulting services, and investment cooperation in asset management. As a result, although the share of total interest income in U.S. banks is relatively small, return on equity remains high, largely due to the fact that non-interest income accounts for approximately 40–50 percent of total income.

In a joint study, R. DeYoung and T. Rice empirically analyzed the relationship between non-interest income and financial performance in U.S. commercial banks. They noted that non-interest income includes asset management services, operations in financial markets, and other financial services. Based on their analysis, they formulated several scientific conclusions. In particular, banks with higher non-interest income exhibited higher returns on assets and equity; however, not all forms of non-interest income were found to be equally stable. For example, commission income demonstrated a more stable trend, while income from financial market activities and brokerage services was characterized by higher volatility and risk. From this perspective, the authors emphasized the need to diversify non-interest income and stabilize its sensitivity to market fluctuations [1].

In a study conducted by J. Schildbach and others, the financial performance of U.S. and European commercial banks was comparatively analyzed, focusing on differences in business models, asset structures, non-interest income trends, and regulatory environments, as well as their impact on returns on assets and equity. The U.S. banking system was found to be distinguished by a business model characterized by a high share of non-interest income, which contributes to higher profitability compared to European banks. In contrast, European banks, despite holding larger asset volumes, exhibit lower profitability due to the persistence of traditional lending models. The authors note that while U.S. banks achieve return on equity levels of around 10–12 percent due to higher non-interest income, European banks, with a greater reliance on interest income, maintain return on equity levels of approximately 7–10 percent [2].

S. Nippani and co-authors examined the relationship between bank size and financial performance in the U.S. banking industry in the period following the global financial crisis of 2008–2009. Their research compared the performance of very large banks, often described as “too big to fail,” with that of medium-sized and small banks. The findings indicate that large banks achieved significantly higher returns on assets and equity than smaller banks. The authors also substantiate the presence of economies of scale, showing that profitability increases as the ratio of operating costs to assets declines. They note that the profitability of small and medium-sized banks is highly dependent on regional factors. At the same time, they emphasize that while large banks demonstrate higher financial performance, they also pose greater systemic risk [3].

In a joint study, O. Batay and others empirically examined the relationship between ESG indicators and financial performance (ROA, ROE, and Tobin’s Q) using panel data on European banks for the period 2009–2018. Their results indicate that green-oriented financial policies positively affected banks’ returns on assets and equity. However, governance-related indicators were found to contribute not to higher profitability but to greater profit stability. Banks that implemented ESG principles not merely as a marketing tool but as part of strategic integration with other sectors achieved higher levels of financial performance. The authors conclude that ESG principles reduce operational risk, enhance reputational advantages, and contribute to higher long-term profitability [4].

In another study, B. Tos and co-authors analyzed the relationship between ESG disclosures and financial stability in European banks. Examining trends for the period 2014–2019, they argue that ESG factors should be regarded not only as an “image” tool but also as a mechanism for mitigating risk. Greater transparency of information reduces the likelihood of banks falling into market risk traps. Their findings indicate that transparency in ESG disclosures contributes to a reduction in systemic and crisis risks. For example, banks with open and standardized ESG indicators exhibited crisis risk levels that were 10–15 percent lower. This positive effect was particularly pronounced among large banks. According to the authors, transparent and standardized ESG disclosure for European banks has evolved from being a “communication cost” into a form of investment in financial stability [5].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is based on data obtained from official statistics of Western countries’ central banks, annual reports of commercial banks, and materials of international financial institutions. The collected data were analyzed using comparative analysis, trend analysis, and logical generalization to assess approaches to ensuring the financial performance of banking activities across different national contexts.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As shown in Figure 1, the volume of income earned by U.S. banks in 2024 varied significantly. Although total income increased compared to previous years, profitability levels displayed signs of instability. This indicates the existence of complexities in asset and liability management within banks. From this perspective, it should be emphasized that banks' financial performance depends not only on direct financial indicators but also on non-financial and external factors influencing banking activities (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Total profits and revenues of major U.S. banks — 2024 results [6]

Certain analyses conducted by the U.S. Federal Reserve on banks' financial statements also reveal aspects related to financial performance. In 2023–2024, U.S. banks experienced negative financial outcomes as total interest expenses exceeded interest income. Although interest income was generated from mortgage lending and reserve securities, it did not reflect sufficient financial performance. In addition, under conditions of increasing payments to depositors, banks' financial performance demonstrated a downward trend, as noted in the analysis [7].

Based on our research and the experience of the U.S. banking system, the following scientific conclusions were formulated.

First, it is necessary to implement measures aimed at strengthening the role of financial markets in increasing the return on banks' assets. In order to reduce the sensitivity of risk-weighted assets to market fluctuations, diversification should be actively pursued.

Second, greater attention should be paid to increasing the share of non-interest income in banks' income structures. In this regard, it is advisable to expand non-interest income primarily through revenues derived from financial intermediation. In other words, priority should be given to developing banks' role as key advisors in investment activities.

Continuing our research, we proceed to analyze banks' financial performance by examining the banking systems of European Union countries. At present, the banking systems of EU member states are distinguished by the application of international regulatory standards and the prioritization of green policy principles. In addition, practical measures are being implemented to enhance financial performance by expanding high-return assets through green lending, reducing risks, and decreasing the share of non-performing loans.

In regulating banking activities, the European banking system relies heavily on Basel III standards. These standards aim to maintain banks' financial stability by requiring capital adequacy (a minimum Tier 1 core capital ratio of at least 10 percent), a liquidity coverage ratio of at least 100 percent under a 30-day stress scenario, and a stable funding ratio of no less than 100 percent.

Currently, European Union banks are implementing their credit policies based on ESG (Environmental, Social, Governance) principles that prioritize green policy objectives. In 2023, approximately 13 percent of EU banks' asset portfolios consisted of financial instruments reflecting green policy criteria. According to Bloomberg Intelligence estimates, the share of "green" assets in EU banks' asset portfolios is projected to reach 20 percent by the end of 2025 [8].

It should be noted that interest rates on green loans in the EU banking system are typically 0.2–0.45 percentage points lower than those on traditional bank loans. As a result, the volume of loans directed toward sustainable green policies exceeded USD 500 billion during 2022–2023. Since 2020, under European Commission regulatory frameworks, the “Green Asset Ratio (GAR)” indicator has been introduced to measure the share of green assets within banks’ loan portfolios. Currently, this ratio stands at approximately 7–8 percent among major European banks. Overall, European banks are increasingly positioning green policy principles as a central element of asset management. The introduction of the green asset ratio indicator has demonstrated that financial performance can no longer be adequately assessed solely on the basis of traditional financial indicators.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In our view, drawing conclusions from the trends observed in the U.S. banking system, it should be emphasized that banks’ financial performance depends on a number of key factors.

First, the stability of non-interest income and its share in total bank revenues. Increasing the volume of non-interest income requires the implementation of measures aimed at expanding banks’ advisory role in financial market participation.

Second, it is important to prevent an excessive increase in interest-based income from assets relative to non-interest income. A comprehensive approach focused on limiting the growth of banks’ risk exposure within their asset portfolios is essential.

Third, ensuring economies of scale plays a significant role. Through policies aimed at bank consolidation and expansion, it is possible to enhance financial performance. From this perspective, banks’ financial performance is directly proportional to the scale of their operations; however, it is also necessary to take into account the accompanying increase in risk exposure.

Turning to the financial performance of the banking systems of European Union countries, several scientific conclusions can be highlighted. Since 2010, European commercial banks have undergone complex transformations. In this context, banks’ profitability and financial stability have become less dependent on interest margins alone and increasingly focused on risk reduction at various levels, the integration of ESG principles, and improvements in asset quality.

First, banks in the European Union maintain a strict stance based on reserve and capital requirements under Basel III. While this approach strengthens financial stability, it may also constrain banks’ profitability levels.

Second, European banks have successfully implemented a transformation by integrating ESG principles into their credit policies. As a result, banks prioritizing ESG principles achieved higher ROA and ROE levels, while operational risks declined. Moreover, greater transparency in ESG disclosures created conditions for reducing crisis risk by 10–15 percent. Consequently, ESG has evolved for European banks from an “image” consideration into a core element of competitive strategy and a tool for risk mitigation.

Third, the introduction of criteria for green lending by European banks has led to a steady increase in the share of green assets over time.

Fourth, alongside the growing importance of non-interest income, the profitability of traditional lending activities appears increasingly constrained.

From this perspective, ESG integration, improvements in asset quality, and strategic risk management are becoming firmly established as the primary drivers of enhanced financial performance in the banking sector.

List of used literature:

1. DeYoung R., Rice T. Noninterest income and financial performance at US commercial banks //Financial review. – 2004. – T. 39. – №. 1. – C. 101-127.
2. Schildbach J. et al. Bank performance in the US and Europe //Deutsche Bank Research. – 2013. – C. 1-20.
3. Nippani S., Ling R. Bank size and performance: An analysis of the industry in the United States in the post-financial-crisis era //Journal of Financial Research. – 2021. – T. 44. – №. 3. – C. 587-606.
4. Bătae O. M., Dragomir V. D., Feleagă L. Environmental, social, governance (ESG), and financial performance of European banks //Accounting and Management Information Systems. – 2020. – T. 19. – №. 3. – C. 480-501.
5. Tóth B. et al. The contribution of ESG information to the financial stability of European banks //Pénzügyi szemle/Public finance quarterly (1963-). – 2021. – T. 66. – №. 3. – C. 429-450.
6. АҚШ банкларининг фойда ва даромадлари ҳажми тенденциялари <https://www.appeconomyinsights.com/p/us-banks-profits-surge>
7. Federal Reserve Banks Combined Financial Statements <https://www.federalreserve.gov/aboutthefed/files/combinedfinstmt2024.pdf>
8. Bloomberg, Green Finance Outlook, 2023

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2025. № 12

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles

Published every monthly

Directions

Social, economic, political, technological, scientific

Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633

CONTACT:

Contact us
+998 50 737 87 88

Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>